

THE USE OF MATH AI APPLICATION: ITS IMPACT ON TEST SCORE IN PRE-CALCULUS AMONG GRADE 11 STEM STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the impact of Math AI applications on test scores in Pre-calculus among grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu. The researchers used descriptive-comparative method as it aims to measure the impact by comparing the students' test scores in Pre-calculus between user and non-user of Math AI applications. One hundred forty-one (141) respondents from grade 11 STEM students were used as a sample size. Survey questionnaire was used to gather the data and it found to be valid and reliable with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.961. The results revealed that Photomath is the most used by STEM 11 students and these students are not exposed to the adoption of Math AI applications in learning pre-calculus. Moreover, students' lack of agreement on the perceive importance of math AI in learning process suggests a general unfamiliarity and limited exposure to Math AI applications among the STEM students. Moreover, the results revealed that there is no significant difference in the test scores of students in Pre-calculus between user and non-user of Math AI applications. Overall, the results imply that while Math AI applications hold potential, their impact remains minimal due to low engagement and possibly insufficient integration into the student's learning process. The researchers recommend students to be provided with greater exposure and guided opportunities to explore and effectively utilize various Math AI applications. Integrating these tools into the teaching-learning process can potentially enhance students' problem-solving skills, support independent learning, and improve their confidence in tackling complex mathematical problems.

Keywords: *Math AI application, Precalculus, and Test Scores*

INTRODUCTION

Learning mathematics before the advent of technology presented many difficulties which could lead to a lack of motivation and interest in learning. Limitation of the access to resources such as textbooks in which learning often relied on what the teacher could provide would discourage students in learning mathematics. Understanding the subject was placed on memorizing formulas and procedures with no calculators or computers to be used. Learning often involved endless drills and repetitive exercises, which could be demotivating for students. Manual calculations, especially with large numbers or complex operations, were time-consuming and prone to errors.

The integration of technology into education, specifically in mathematics, has changed how students learn and interact with mathematical content. One of the most significant transformations is the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. AI-powered learning tools have been developed to provide interactive and personalized learning experiences. In the context of mathematics, Math AI applications such as Photomath, Gauthmath, GeoGebra, and others offer students step-by-step solutions, real-time feedback, and conceptual explanations that aim to support independent and guided learning (Hwang & Tu, 2021; Mohamed et al., 2022).

These applications are designed not only to assist in solving equations but also to enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts. For senior high school students taking Pre-calculus—a foundational course for higher-level mathematics—these tools can potentially bridge gaps in learning and improve performance. As the Philippines continues to integrate digital technology into its educational systems, understanding the impact of Math AI tools on student performance becomes increasingly relevant (Melchor et al., 2023).

Despite the growing availability of such tools, their actual usage and impact on academic performance remain underexplored, especially in regions with limited digital access or exposure. At Mindanao State University-Sulu, the use of Math AI applications among Grade 11 STEM students is still emerging. This presents an opportunity to investigate how these tools are being adopted, their perceived usefulness, and whether they contribute to improved academic outcomes in pre-calculus (Inoferio et al., 2024).

This study aims to examine the use of Math AI applications and assess their impact on the pre-calculus test scores of Grades 11 STEM students. It seeks to answer questions about which applications are most used, how many students utilize them, how important these tools are perceived to be, and whether there is a significant difference in academic performance between users and non-users of such applications. By doing so, the study hopes to shed light on the role of technology in supporting math education at the senior high school level.

Emerging literature highlights the growing effectiveness of AI-based tools in education, with some studies indicating improvements in student engagement, self-confidence, and problem-solving skills (Rane, 2023; Bešlić et al., 2024). However, the results are not universally conclusive, and some scholars caution that over-reliance on AI

may hinder deep conceptual understanding. These mixed perspectives underscore the need for localized research to understand the effects within specific student populations and educational contexts (Wardat et al., 2023).

In this light, the researchers explore the extent to which Grade 11 STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu utilize Math AI applications, and whether their usage correlates with improved performance in pre-calculus. Given the importance of this subject in the STEM curriculum, understanding factors that influence learning and performance can inform both teaching strategies and policy decisions regarding educational technology integration.

Finally, this research aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on AI in education, with a specific focus on mathematics learning in a Philippine public senior high school context. The insights derived may help educators, administrators, and policymakers make informed decisions about the implementation and support of AI tools in mathematics instruction.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine Math AI application: its effect to test score in Pre-calculus in Mindanao State University-Sulu senior high school students in grade 11 STEM. The following research question will guide this study:

1. What math AI application is commonly used by students in Mindanao State University-Sulu senior high school students in grade 11 STEM?
2. What is the frequency of students identified as users and non-users of Math AI applications?
3. What is the importance of Math AI applications used in learning?
4. Is there a significant difference in the test scores of students when based on their usage of Math AI applications?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-comparative method to determine the impact of math AI applications on test scores in Pre-calculus among Grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University-Sulu.

According to Siedlecki (2020), descriptive research looks at the organization and characteristics of a given organization or population, and it can provide a description of events that evolve over time.

Research Site

The research is conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu approximately 1.5 km away from center of Jolo. It specifically involved the grade 11 STEM students from three sections, whose classrooms are situated beside the gymnasium and the school cafeteria.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study are the grade 11 STEM students currently enrolled in Mindanao State University-Sulu senior high school. The total population of STEM 11 students is 141. The researchers then used Rao soft calculator in determining the sample size of the respondents. Table 1 below shows the number of respondents as determined with the use of stratified random sampling.

Table 1. Number of Respondents in each Section

Section	Population	Sample
STEM 1-11	43	30
STEM 2-11	47	33
STEM 3-11	51	35
Total	141	98

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a survey questionnaire to get the information from the respondents which is used to achieve the objectives of the study. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: part one focused on identifying the commonly used Math AI by students, and part two will assess the perceive importance of Math AI applications in the learning process. The questionnaire was found valid and reliable were the Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.961

Research Ethics Protocol

The researchers carefully examined the ethical considerations related to the research. The research ensured informed consent and addressed any potential conflicts of interest. Respondents were provided with detailed information about the research, ensuring they had a clear understanding of their participation. Respondents confirmed that respondents were fully informed about how their data would be used and the potential outcomes of the research. Importantly, respondents retained the right to refuse participation and were not pressured to give their approval.

Data Collection

The researchers submitted a letter duly approved by their adviser to the director of senior high school in Mindanao State University-Sulu to seek permission. After having been approved, the survey questionnaire was administered to the selected grade 11 STEM students during their free time. The students were briefed and have given five minutes to write their answers. It was assured that their responses to every question will be strictly kept with utmost confidentiality. The filled-out survey questionnaires were retrieved right after the given time.

Statistical Technique

For the interpretation of data, the researchers used frequency count and percentages to identify the commonly used math AI applications by grade 11 STEM students in Mindanao State University- Sulu and to determine the counts of students as categorized into user and non-user of math AI applications. Also, the researchers used median to determine the perceive importance of math AI applications as used in learning process. Lastly, Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine the significant difference on the test scores in Pre-calculus of students when based on their usage of Math AI applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Math AI Applications used by STEM Students

Math AI	Frequency	Percent
1. Photomath	35	30.7
2. Gauthmath	11	9.6
3. Math X	3	2.6
4. Mathos AI	1	0.9
5. Geo Gebra	1	0.9
6. Algebrator	1	0.9

Table 2 shows the Math AI applications commonly used by STEM students in Mindanao State University- Sulu. Out of one-hundred fourteen (114) respondents, Photomath was used by Thirty-Five (35) students or (30.7%) of the total population, Gauthmath users are eleven (11) or (9.6%), Math X users are three (3) students or (2.6%), the Mathos AI, Geo Gebra, and Algebrator has generated only one (1) user of each or (0.9%) of the respondents. Some of the respondents used not only one Math AI application. The result revealed that Photomath is the most used by STEM 11 students.

A study conducted at Bukidnon State University explored the utilization of Photomath among second-year students in calculus courses. The findings highlighted

that student found Photomath to be user-friendly and beneficial for learning support, emphasizing its accessibility and inclusivity (Luzano et.al., 2024).

Table 3. Counts of Students as classified to Users and Non-users of Math AI Applications

Students Type	Frequency	Percent
Math AI applications users	40	35.1
Math AI applications non-users	74	64.9
Total	114	100.0

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage of STEM students when categorized as Math AI applications users and non-users. As shown in the table, STEM students who belong to Math AI applications users are 40 or 35.1% percent of the total population while Math AI applications non-users are 74 or 64.9% percent. This means that approximately one-third of the respondents are Math AI applications users. This suggests that STEM students are not exposed to the adoption of Math AI applications in learning pre-calculus.

Students' adoption of AI-based teacher-bots in higher education is influenced by perceived ease of use, usefulness, personalization, interactivity, trust, anthropomorphism, and intelligence, but negatively influenced by their stickiness to human teachers (Pillai et. Al., 2023).

Table 4 Importance of Math AI applications as used in learning Pre-calculus

Indicators	Md	Description
1. I use Math AI applications to help me determine the step-by-step solutions of Pre-Calculus problems.	3.00	Undecided
2. Math AI applications save my time in studying Pre-Calculus.	3.00	Undecided
3. I can solve Pre-Calculus problems more rapidly when using AI-powered math application.	3.00	Undecided
4. I used math AI applications to assist with my homework in Pre-Calculus.	3.00	Undecided
5. I used math AI applications to solve Pre-Calculus problems I couldn't solve on my own.	3.00	Undecided
6. I felt more confident in my Pre-Calculus abilities after using math AI	3.00	Undecided
7. I keep using Math AI to practice answering more problems in Pre-Calculus.	3.00	Undecided

8. I refer to Math AI applications to understand concepts in Pre-Calculus better.	3.00	Undecided
9. I refer to Math AI to supplement my teacher's instruction.	3.00	Undecided
10. I used math AI applications to check the answer of my activities in Pre-Calculus.	3.00	Undecided
11. I used Math AI to get personalized help/feedback.	3.00	Undecided
12. I refer to Math AI because I don't have access to other help (e.g., tutoring)	3.00	Undecided
13. Math AI makes me engaged in learning mathematics.	3.00	Undecided

Note: 5 = Strongly Agree, 4 = Agree, 3 = Undecided, 2 = Disagree, 1 = Strongly Disagree

Table 4 displays the level of agreement of STEM students on the perceived importance of Math AI as used in learning pre-calculus. The researchers used median in determining the agreement of the respondents. As presented in the table, all respondents were *undecided* if Math AI is important to be applied in learning the subject. This lack of agreement suggests a general unfamiliarity and limited exposure to Math AI applications among the STEM students.

A study by Chan and Hu (2023) revealed that undergraduate students often have misconceptions about generative AI (GenAI), with varied definitions and understandings of its applications. This lack of clarity can lead to uncertainty in recognizing the value of AI tools in educational contexts.

Table 5. Mann Whitney U test to compare students' test scores in Pre-calculus Between User and Non-User of Math AI Applications

Students' Type	N	Mean Rank	<i>U</i>	<i>W</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Math AI non-user	74	59.14	1358.500	2178.500	-.723	.470
Math AI User	40	54.46				

*Significant at $p < 0.05$.

Table 5 presents the significant difference on the test score of students in pre-calculus when based on their usage of Math AI applications. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the test scores of students in pre-calculus between Math AI applications non-user ($N = 74$, mean rank = 59.14) and Math AI applications user ($N = 40$, mean rank = 54.46); $U = 1358.500$, $W = 2178.500$, $Z = -.723$, $p = .470$. The results suggest that the use of Math AI applications has no impact on the test scores of students in pre-calculus.

A quantitative study examined the impact of AI-based systems on mathematics achievement in rural contexts. The findings indicated that while AI-led and traditional teacher-led instructions both improved student performance, there was no significant difference between the two approaches. This underscores that AI tools may not always outperform conventional teaching methods (Khazanchi et. Al., 2025).

Conclusions

The researchers conclude that Photomath appeared as the most used application, yet only about one-third of the respondents reported using any Math AI tools at all. The findings revealed that STEM students at Mindanao State University-Sulu remain unexposed in adopting Math AI applications.

Based on the findings, respondents were found undecided on the importance of Math AI applications. Hence, this concludes that their lack of agreement suggests that students have limited exposure and are not familiar with such technology.

Furthermore, results revealed that there was no significant difference in the Pre-calculus test scores between users and non-users of Math AI applications. This suggests that the current use of Math AI tools does not have an impact on the test scores of the students in Pre-calculus. Overall, the results imply that while Math AI applications hold potential, their impact remains minimal due to low engagement and possibly insufficient integration into the students' learning process.

Recommendations

Based on the result, the researchers recommended the following:

Research Agenda

1. Teachers may provide more activities and integrate these tools into the teaching-learning process to enhance students' problem-solving skills, support independent learning, and improve their confidence in tackling complex mathematical problems.
2. Students may be provided with greater exposure and guided opportunities to explore and effectively utilize various Math AI applications.
3. Future Researchers may explore the specific ways if Math AI applications are significant to the students in Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School grade 11 STEM strand.

Research Problem

Based on the findings of this study, the following topics are recommended by the researchers to the future researchers.

1. Investigate the impact of math AI application on academic performance of grade 11 stem students.

2. Examine the impact of math AI applications on student engagement and motivation in learning precalculus
3. Explore the long-term effect of using math-AI Applications on student learning outcomes in mathematics.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers uphold that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was duly obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, and they were clearly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were strictly maintained, and every effort was made to safeguard their well-being throughout the research process. The researchers declare that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Additionally, the interpretation of the findings was carried out with objectivity, without bias, and the results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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